

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D8.2 – Project Website and Web2.0 Channels

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BigDataOcean Project Profile

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Acronym:	BigDataOcean
Title:	Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications
URL:	http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/
Start Date:	01/01/2017
Duration:	30 months

Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	Exmile Solutions Limited (EXMILE)	United Kingdom
	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (UBONN)	Germany
	Centro de Investigação em Energia REN – State Grid, S.A. – R&D Nester (NESTER)	Portugal
	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	Foinikas Shipping Company (FOINIKAS)	Greece
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1 Project Website and Web2.0 Channels

1.1 Project Website

The project's website is up and running since the 1st month of the project. The figure below shows the content presented at the home page of the project (i.e. <http://www.bigdataocean.eu/site/>).

Figure 1-1: Big Data Ocean website homepage

As depicted in the figure, besides the home page, news, events, newsletter and "contact us" are also available at the website's menu. Figure 1-2 and Figure 1-3 depict the content of the news and event pages (as captured on 06/03/2017). Events page lists all the events that are organised by the project partners and the ones that projects partners have attended (e.g. Networking and Info Days organised by the European Commission, workshops, conferences, etc.). News page includes all the news that are considered relevant to the project. Finally, it is noted that the homepage includes a link to the project's private area, where username/password are requested from the site in order to authorise access to restricted material to the user.

Figure 1-2: Big Data Ocean website events page

Figure 1-3: Big Data Ocean website news page

1.2 Web 2.0 Channels

BigDataOcean has established a set of social media accounts so as to maximise the visibility of the project and optimise the communication with the user communities which are linked to the project's achievements. In the following subsections, we briefly provide a description of those accounts and the benefits the project is expecting from each one of them.

1.2.1 Twitter

A Twitter account¹, depicted in Figure 1-4 below, has established for the BigDataOcean from the early beginning of the project (i.e., January 2017) to facilitate a global communication in a measurable and inexpensive manner, and to make use of this fast and straightforward way to communicate with stakeholders, also at conferences, workshops and seminars. This medium is being used to reach out to a broader community making use of the Twitter snowball effect, to share news and thoughts on ongoing research and other findings in the project, and to follow interesting conversations and be part of them. Over the first three months of the project, BigDataOcean posted 12 tweets, has 44 followers and follows 7 people on Twitter.

The use of Twitter is expected to be intensified over the next period so as to communicate upcoming events (e.g. the ICE conference), inform on software releases, share interesting readings and address the audience with questions to gather input on some of the key issues covered by the project.

The use of Twitter is also expected to be beneficial for the acquisition of new subscribers to the project's newsletter, as newsletter feed will be followed by a tweet which directs the audience to the newsletter and the subscription form.

Figure 1-4: Big Data Ocean twitter account

1.2.2 Facebook

BigDataOcean created a Facebook page², depicted in Figure 1-5 below, to increase the visibility and the communication means of the project. This medium is being used to reach out a broader community through posting project's news, activities and key findings. BigDataOcean's posts at the Facebook page will be usually redirecting to news/activities posted in the project's website, linking thus the facebook

¹ https://twitter.com/big_data_ocean

² https://twitter.com/big_data_ocean

page to content posted in the project's website. BigDataOcean has made 9 posts to the page, has 18 followers and 16 likes, over the first three months of the project.

Figure 1-5: Big Data Ocean facebook page

1.2.3 LinkedIn

BigDataOcean has set up a group on the LinkedIn³ social media platform depicted in Figure 1-6 below. This channel is not the main focus with regards to dissemination but rather used to trigger discussions with our stakeholder communities that frequently use this medium. Thus, our LinkedIn group acts as a portal through which people can find a link to the project website and further request information to the project's activities. During the first three months of BigDataOcean, 16 members have joined the project's group at LinkedIn.

Figure 1-6: Big Data Ocean LinkedIn group

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13505618>